

Generic Protocol for Environmental Health Systematic Reviews Based on COSTER Recommendations

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Systematic Reviews

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ABSTRACT

A protocol template to help researchers follow the [COSTER recommendations](#) for conduct of systematic reviews. This instance covers the planning steps of a systematic review and will help with writing up the systematic review protocol.

The intent is to convert COSTER from a checklist of things which need to be done into a sequence of actions which can be followed by a research team.

When completing the protocol and either registering it or submitting it to a journal, please cite this instance of the protocol template and the parent manuscript, DOI [10.1016/j.envint.2020.105926](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105926).

EXTERNAL LINK

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016041202031881X>

THIS PROTOCOL ACCOMPANIES THE FOLLOWING PUBLICATION

Whaley, Paul, Elisa Aiassa, Claire Beausoleil, Anna Beronius, Gary Bilotta, Alan Boobis, Rob de Vries, et al. 2020. "Recommendations for the Conduct of Systematic Reviews in Toxicology and Environmental Health Research (COSTER)." Environment International 143 (July): 105926.

PROTOCOL STATUS

In development

This is the first attempt at developing a generic protocol based on the COSTER recommendations. Feedback is very welcome!

Started on Mar 16, 2021 17:44:13

Finished steps: 42

Securing capacity, competencies, and tools

Step 1 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:57:13

1 Assess the team's combined competence in conduct of a systematic review. *Recommendation 1.1.1.*

A	B
Competency	Team member(s) (initials)
Information science (for e.g. search strategies)	JM
Evidence appraisal methods (i.e. risk of bias assessment)	OVM, AK, MS
Statistical methods	MS
Domain or subject expertise	AK, SE, MS, OVM
Systematic review methods	OVM

Team member competencies

Step 2 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:57:26

2 Identify information management practices and tools for each stage of the review. *Recommendation 1.1.2.*

A	B
Information management component	Tools or packages
Reference manager	Citavi
Knowledge management tool	Cadima
Systematic review software	NA
Statistics software and packages	NA
Artificial Intelligence support tools (e.g. for screening)	NA

Information management tools and packages

Step 3 completed on Mar 26, 2021 15:57:50

3 List the potential conflicts of interest of the authors. *Recommendations 1.1.3 and 1.1.4.*

This should include both financial and non-financial interests which readers should be aware of in order to understand the motivations of the authors of the review.

By listing the interests as *potential*, you are confirming that they are not *apparent* conflicts of interest, i.e. they cannot reasonably be expected to compromise the integrity of the systematic review. People with apparent conflicts of interest should be excluded from decision-making roles in the review.

Interests should be declared using the ICMJE Conflict of Interest Disclosure Forms, as attached. The summary statements generated by the forms for each author can be copy-pasted into the table. [ICMJE COI Disclosure Form.pdf](#)

A	B
Author	ICMJE COI Summary
Olwenn Martin	Dr. Martin has nothing to disclose.
Martin Scholze	Mr. Scholze has nothing to disclose.
Sibylle Ermler	Dr. Ermler has nothing to disclose.
Asma Baig	Dr. Baig has nothing to disclose.
Andreas Kortenkamp	Dr. Kortenkamp has nothing to disclose.

Summary statements of authors declared conflicts of interest.

Setting the research question ("problem formulation")

Step 4 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:20:34

4 Demonstrate the need for a new review. *Recommendation 1.2.1*

Step 4.1 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:20:34

4.1 Describe the scientific value of the question(s), i.e. why it is important that it be investigated.

Step 4.2 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:20:34

4.2 Describe the importance to stakeholders of the question(s) being asked.

Step 4.3 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:20:34

4.3 Summarise relevant existing primary research and evidence syntheses to justify conducting a new systematic review.

Step 5 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:21:46

5 **Articulate the scientific rationale for each question via development of a theoretical framework.** *Recommendation 1.2.2.* For example, this would describe how the exposure is related to the outcomes of interest if the systematic review is an investigation of an exposure-outcome relationship. The theoretical framework should include discussion of the biological plausibility of the relationship being investigated.

Step 6 completed on Mar 26, 2021 14:46:20

6 **For each research question to be answered by the review, prospectively define a statement of the research objective in terms of Population, Exposure or Intervention, Comparator, Outcome, Study Design, and Target Condition, selected as appropriate.** *Recommendation 1.2.3.*

- Authors may wish to refer to Morgan et al. 2018 for guidance on how to formulate research questions as PECO statements. Conceiving of an ideal study may also help characterise the PECO elements which define what type of study will be informative for your review findings.

Morgan RL, Whaley P, Thayer KA, Schünemann HJ (2018). Identifying the PECO: A framework for formulating good questions to explore the association of environmental and other exposures with health outcomes.. Environment international. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.07.015>

Step 6.1 completed on Mar 26, 2021 14:40:24

6.1 **Define the target Population of interest.** These are the objects of investigation, i.e. the entities to which exposures or interventions happen.

A	B
Species	Humans or other mammalian species
Sex	Male
Age	Adults of reproductive age
Health status	No underlying conditions known to affect sperm parameters
Additional characteristics	

Characteristics of the population of interest. Add rows to cover other population characteristics relevant to the SR question.

Step 6.2 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:36:59

6.2

Define the target Exposure or Intervention of interest. This concerns the administered or observed change in conditions of the objects of investigation. It should include timing, duration and dose.

A	B	C
Exposure or intervention	Exposure to BPA (measured in urine in human studies)	Oral exposure in animal studies (gavage, dietary or via drinking water)
Timing	In expectant mothers or shortly before sperm measurement in adults.	Perinatally in other mammals
Duration	Not specified	Not specified
Dose	All doses	All doses

Timing, duration and dose of the exposure / intervention. Add rows to cover other exposure / intervention characteristics relevant to the SR question. Add a new table for each exposure or intervention of interest.

Step 6.3 completed on Mar 16, 2021 18:11:15

6.3

Define the target Comparator of interest. This concerns the characteristics of the exposure or intervention being used as the comparator to which the target exposure or intervention is being compared.

A	B
Comparator	Either sufficient information reported to allow comparison/categorisation of exposures (human studies) or control group (experimental animal studies).
Timing	In expectant mothers or shortly before sperm measurements in human adults. Perinatally in other mammals.
Duration	Not relevant
Dose	Men not exposed to BPA or BPA exposure in lower quartiles. In animal experiments, control group (no exposure or exposure to control).

Timing, duration and dose of the comparator. Add rows to cover other comparator characteristics relevant to the SR question.

Step 6.4 completed on Mar 26, 2021 14:46:13

- 6.4 Define the target Outcome(s) of interest.** This concerns the change being measured in the exposure or intervention group. These should be the primary outcomes of interest to the systematic review which form the hypothesis or hypotheses being tested. Secondary outcomes can also be listed.

A	B	C	D	E	F
Semen quality	Total sperm count	Sperm concentration	Sperm motility	Sperm morphology	Sperm vitality

Primary outcomes of interest. Add new rows for each outcome of interest.

Step 6.5 skipped on Mar 26, 2021 14:46:20

- 6.5 Define the Target Condition.** This is the object of a test method for diagnosis or detection. It is only necessary for a systematic review of a diagnostic or detection test method.

Target condition characteristic 1	
Target condition characteristic 2	

Defining the eligibility criteria and designing the process for screening evidence for inclusion

Step 7 completed on Mar 26, 2021 15:23:10

- 7 Define and justify unambiguous and appropriate eligibility criteria** for each component of the objective statement.
Recommendation 1.3.1, 1.3.3, 1.3.4, 1.3.5

A	B	C
PECO element	Description of eligibility criteria for epidemiological studies	Description of eligibility criteria for animal experimental studies
Eligible populations	Younger than 40 years, older than 18 years	Mammalian species
Eligible exposures	Bisphenol A exposures measured as urinary concentrations.	Administered by gavage, via drinking water or through the diet; at least 2 exposure doses.
Eligible comparators	Sufficient information reported to allow comparison/categorisation of exposures.	Control group (same species as exposure group(s))
Eligible primary outcomes	Total sperm count, sperm concentration, sperm motility, sperm morphology, sperm vitality	Total sperm count, sperm concentration, sperm motility, sperm morphology, sperm vitality
Eligible secondary outcomes	NA	
Eligible study designs	Case control studies, cohort studies, cross sectional studies	Experimental in vivo studies

Describe the eligibility criteria for each PECO element. Add additional PECO elements as appropriate.

A	B	C	D
PECO element	Description of exclusion criteria for epidemiological studies	Description of exclusion criteria for animal studies	Reasons for exclusion
Excluded populations	Men with non-descended testes, hypospadias, and chronic diseases such as cancer, varicocele, or other known illnesses impacting on semen quality; men > 40 years; < 18 years	Non mammalian test species such as fish or amphibians	These conditions are known to impact semen quality and may confound effects. For animals, lack of human relevance of non-mammalian species.
Excluded exposures	Bisphenol A in other body fluids or tissues, e.g. plasma or seminal fluid, exposure information derived from questionnaires or job exposure matrices	Administered subcutaneously or intraperitoneally; only 1 exposure dose group; in juveniles or adults.	Measurements in e.g. plasma or seminal fluids are not deemed sufficiently reliable (matrix interferences) and do not currently permit the estimation of daily intakes that have resulted in these concentrations. In Naimal studies, other modes of administration will circumvent first-pass metabolism.
Excluded comparators	Insufficient information reported to allow comparison/categorisation of exposures.	No control group	The objective of the SR is the derivation of a safety threshold/reference dose.
Excluded outcomes	Sperm DNA damage, aneuploidies, measures of in vitro fertilization success, time to pregnancy	Sperm DNA damage, aneuploidies, measures of in vitro fertilization success, time to pregnancy	These effects are not related to disruptions of male reproductive health by hormonal factors

Describe the criteria for exclusion of studies, according to each PECO element. Add additional PECO elements as appropriate.

8 **Define the points at which screening for eligibility will take place.** *Recommendation 1.3.2.* Will there be screening at title and abstract, full text, or both?

A
Points at which screening will take place
Describe whether there will be screening at title and abstract, full text, or both

Points at which screening will take place

Step 9 completed on Mar 26, 2021 15:25:52

9 **Include all relevant, publicly-available evidence,** except for research for which there is insufficient methodological information to allow appraisal of internal validity. *Recommendation 1.3.6.* **Exclude evidence which is not publicly available.** *Recommendation 1.3.9*

A
Policy on eligibility of grey literature and unpublished evidence
Although grey literature is not strictly excluded, the search strategy does not include sources specifically targeting the grey literature. Evidence which is not publicly available is excluded.

Policy on grey literature for the systematic review.

COSTER recommends that grey literature (i.e. studies that have not been published in peer-reviewed journals) should be included in systematic reviews. This is because the relevance of evidence is determined by the SR objectives, not by the publication status of that evidence, the language the evidence is in, nor its compatibility with the analyses planned by the reviewers.

Only publicly available information about a study should be eligible for inclusion. If the planned SR will bring into the public domain evidence which was previously inaccessible, this makes the evidence eligible for inclusion.

Studies for which there is insufficient information for risk of bias to be evaluated should be excluded from a SR, to prevent the inclusion in a SR of evidence that is potentially misleading but cannot be identified as such by the reviewers.

Step 10 failed on Mar 26, 2021 15:27:09

10 **Include evidence which is relevant to review objectives irrespective of whether its results are in a usable form.** *Recommendation 1.3.7*

A
Policy on eligibility of studies with unusable data
To align with specific objectives of this SR, only studies with usable data will be included.

COSTER recommends that documents be included in a SR regardless of whether their data fit the analysis plan of the reviewers or they are in a language in which the reviewers are fluent. This is to ensure that study documents which may contain information of potential relevance to the SR's research objectives are not excluded from the data extraction step of the SR; however, they may be excluded from specific synthesis steps such as meta-analysis.

Step 11 failed on Mar 26, 2021 16:41:05

11 Include relevant evidence irrespective of language. *Recommendation 1.3.8.*

A
Policy on eligibility of studies based on language
Due to resource limitations, only reports in English will be considered.

Policy on language

A
Languages to be included in the systematic review
English

List of included languages in the systematic review

Step 12 completed on Mar 26, 2021 15:50:18

12 Do not exclude multiple reports of the same research (e.g. multiple publications, conference abstracts etc.); instead collate the methodological information from each of the reports as part of the data extraction process for each unit of evidence. *Recommendation 3.4*

A
Multiple publications policy
Multiple reports of the same research will not be excluded, instead the methodological information from each of the reports will be collated as part of the data extraction process for each unit of evidence.

Policy on handling of multiple publications from same study

Step 13 completed on Mar 26, 2021 16:45:02

13 Screening of each piece of evidence for inclusion to be conducted by at least two people working independently, with an appropriate process (e.g. third-party arbitration) for identifying and settling disputes. *Recommendation 3.1*

A	B
Team members who will conduct screening	Method for resolving disputes
AK, OM, ES and AB will carry out the screening. As part of an initial consistency check, 200 studies will first be screened by all team members in parallel. Eligibility criteria will be applied to the remainder of the merged reference list by one team member.. The full text of the resulting list of included references after title/abstract screening will then be examined for inclusion in duplicate, i.e. by two team members independently. The reason for exclusion of studies after assessment of the full text will be recorded.	Discrepancies detected during the pilot stage will be reviewed by all team members and the eligibility criteria will be clarified if necessary.

Planned approach to duplicate screening and dispute resolution

Step 14 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:54:34

14 Design the PRISMA flow chart for presentation of the results of the screening process. *Recommendation 3.2*

Step 15 completed on Mar 16, 2021 17:54:46

15 Pilot test the screening process. *Recommendation 1.4.7*

A generic protocol for piloting the screening stage of a systematic review is available here:
<https://www.protocols.io/view/a-general-protocol-for-pilot-testing-the-screening-bkc9ksz6>

Defining the strategy for searching for evidence relevant to the review objectives

Step 16 completed on Mar 26, 2021 16:52:17

16 Design sufficiently sensitive search criteria, so that studies which meet the eligibility criteria of the review are not inadvertently excluded. Document the search methods in sufficient detail to render them transparent and reproducible. *Recommendations 1.4.1, 2.6*

Step 16.1 completed on Mar 26, 2021 16:47:11

16.1 Search all the key scientific databases for the topic, including national, regional and subject-specific databases. *Recommendation 2.1*

A
List of databases
PubMed
Web of Science
Scopus
Science Direct

List of databases searched in the systematic review

Step 16.2 completed on Mar 26, 2021 16:51:07

2d

16.2 Structure search strategies for each database, electronic and other source, using appropriate controlled vocabulary, free-text terms and logical operators in a manner which prioritises sensitivity. Document the search methods and results in sufficient detail to render them transparent and reproducible. *Recommendations 2.3, 2.6*

A	B
Database	Search strategy
PubMed	((80-05-7[rn] OR bisphenol a[tiab] OR 2,2-(4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl)propane[tiab] OR 2,2-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane[tiab] OR 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyldimethylmethane[tiab] OR 4,4'-isopropylidene diphenol[tiab] OR 4,4'-isopropylidenebisphenol[tiab] OR 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol[tiab] OR biphenol a[tiab] OR bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane[tiab] OR bisphenol[tiab] OR bisphenol-a[tiab] OR diphenylolpropane[tiab] OR p,p'-dihydroxydiphenylpropane [tiab] OR 4,4'-isopropylidene diphenol[nm] OR bisphenol a[nm])) AND ((sperm[MeSH Terms] OR semen[MeSH Terms])
Web of Science	(80-05-7 OR bisphenol a OR 2,2-(4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl)propane OR 2,2-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane OR 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyldimethylmethane OR 4,4'-isopropylidene diphenol OR 4,4'-isopropylidenebisphenol OR 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol OR biphenol a OR bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane bisphenol OR bisphenol-a OR diphenylolpropane OR p,p'-dihydroxydiphenylpropane OR 4,4'-isopropylidene diphenol) AND (*sperm* OR *semen* OR *semin* OR *fertil*)
Scopus	((CHEMNAME (4,4'-isopropylidene diphenol)) OR (CHEMNAME (bisphenol a))) OR (CHEMNAME (bisphenol)) OR (CHEMNAME (4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol)) OR (CHEMNAME (4,4'-isopropylidene diphenol)) OR (CHEMNAME (bisphenol a)) OR (CASREGNUMBER (80-05-7))) AND ((TITLE-ABS-KEY (*sperm*)) OR (TITLE-ABSKEY (*semen*)) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY (*semin*)))
Science Direct	Title, abstract, keywords: (BPA OR Bisphenol A) AND (sperm OR semen OR seminal)

Search strategy for each database in the systematic review

Atkinson KM, Koenka AC, Sanchez CE, Moshontz H, Cooper H (2015). Reporting standards for literature searches and report inclusion criteria: making research syntheses more transparent and easy to replicate.. Research synthesis methods. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1127>

16.3 Define reproducible strategies for identifying and searching sources of grey literature (databases, websites etc.). Document the search methods and results in sufficient detail to render them transparent and reproducible. *Recommendations 2.2 and 2.6*

Grey literature source	Search strategy	Date of search	No. of results

Search strategy for each source of grey literature in the review

16.4 Search within the reference lists of included studies and other reviews relevant to the topic (“hand-searching”) and consider searching in the reference lists of documents which have cited included studies. **Search by contacting relevant individuals and organisations.** *Recommendations 2.4 and 2.5*

A	B
Supplementary search strategies	Indicate if will be used
Hand search references of included studies	yes
Hand search references of relevant reviews	yes
Hand search references of studies cited by included studies	yes
By contacting individuals and organisations	no
Other	no

Supplementary search strategies

17 Plan for re-running all searches and screen the results for potentially eligible studies within 12 months prior to publication of the review (screening at least at the level of title plus abstract). *Recommendation 2.7*

A	B
Timing	Searches will be re-run if the results are not published within 12 months of the original search. Additionally, a search alert has been set up in Web of Science for the search string given above.
Sources	PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, Science Direct.
Level of screening	Title and abstract
Updating findings	If the findings of a new published study are likely to alter the conclusions of the work, findings will be updated.

Policy for updating searches

Methods for synthesising and evaluating the evidence

Step 18 completed on Mar 26, 2021 18:08:59

18 Design the "characteristics of included studies" table. *Recommendation 1.4.2*

Step 19 completed on Mar 26, 2021 16:55:04

19 Design and pilot the data extraction forms. *Recommendation 1.4.7*

Step 20 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:26:39

20 Define the risk of bias assessment methods to be used for evaluating the internal validity of the included research. If observational studies are included, this should cover identification of plausible confounders. *Recommendation 1.4.3*

Review teams may find the **FEAT** (Focus-Extent-Application-Transparency) mnemonic to be useful in defining their risk of bias assessment methods.

- **Focus:** The focus of the tool should be exclusively the internal validity of a study. If other quality constructs are of interest, each should be assessed in a separate process.
- **Extent:** All the important threats to internal validity should be covered by the tool. If observational studies are being appraised, the threats should include all important confounders.
- **Application:** The appraisal process should produce consistent, accurate descriptions of the extent to which a study is vulnerable to each identified threat to internal validity. The judgements should be in a form which can be logically incorporated into the evidence synthesis.

- **Transparency:** The reason for each judgement should be documented, quoting as justification relevant text from the study documentation.

Refer to Section 5 of the COSTER recommendations for detail on how the risk of bias assessment process should be conducted.

Step 20.1 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:26:39

20.1 Define the tool selection and modification process (how will a suitable tool be identified, and what process will be followed to identify and validate any necessary modifications?) *Recommendation 1.4.3*

A	B	C	D
Tool selected	Studies to which it is applied	Modifications made	Method for validating modifications
Cochrane Risk of Bias in Non-randomized Studies (ROBINS) of interventions (ROBINS-I) as modified by Radke et al (2018) for the health effects of phthalate exposure	Epidemiological studies	Minor adaptations to reflect issues pertaining to BPA exposure and semen parameters	Not validated
NTP OHAT Risk-of-bias tool as adapted by EFSA (2017, 2019)	Animal experimental studies	Additional elements will be considered; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of polycarbonate-free caging • Use of phytoestrogen-free chow • Demonstration that a positive control was effective 	This is recommended by EFSA (2019) to avoid confounding and contamination of control animals.

Selection of tools to be used in systematic review

Step 20.2 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:07:22

20.2 Risk of bias assessment is to be conducted by at least two people working independently, with an appropriate process (e.g. third-party arbitration) for identifying and settling disputes. *Recommendation 5.3*

A	B
Team members conducting risk of bias assessment	Method for identifying and settling disputes
AK, OM with some overlap	In discussion with AK

Approach to conducting risk of bias assessment

Step 20.3 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:07:40

20.3 Define the training and piloting process for the risk of bias assessment (how will the review team be trained in use of the tool, and what are the conditions under which the piloting process will be determined satisfactory?) *Recommendation 1.4.7*

Step 21 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:33:46

21 Design the methods for synthesising the included studies, to cover: qualitative and quantitative methods (with full consideration given to synthesis methods to be used when meta-analysis is not possible); assessment of heterogeneity; choice of effect measure (e.g. RR, OR etc.); methods for meta-analysis and other quantitative synthesis; pre-defined, appropriate effect modifiers for sub-group analyses. *Recommendations 1.4.4, 6.1*

A	B
Synthesis Component	Planned Methods
Qualitative or narrative methods	<p>Following the principles developed in the EFSA (2017) Guidance on the use of weight of evidence in scientific assessments, in each qualitative synthesis (human studies and animal studies) we will consider aspects of an association that may suggest causation, as detailed in the Bradford Hill criteria: consistency, exposure–response relationship, strength of association, temporal relationship, biological plausibility, and coherence.</p> <p>We will distinguish between conflicting evidence (unexplained positive and negative results in similarly exposed human populations or in similar animal models) and differing results (mixed results attributable to differences between human populations, animal models, or exposure conditions). We will synthesise human studies by adopting the framework developed by Radke et al. (2018).</p> <p>Animal studies will be synthesised according to the framework used by Radke et al. (2018), modified in line with EFSA (2019).</p>

Quantitative methods	To achieve integration of evidence to arrive at quantitative assessment allowing us to derive a reference dose with respect to endpoint semen quality we will follow the procedure sketched out in EFSA (2017). Briefly, qualitative comparisons will be made for each line of evidence (per animal species, rat or mouse, and human) where it is possible to derive a point of departure (NOAEL or benchmark dose). These comparisons will be based on high quality studies (high or medium confidence human studies, Tier 1 animal studies). We will then select the study (or studies) for the most sensitive species and derive a reference dose.
Conditions for combining studies in overall and subgroup analyses	
Choice of effect measure	The primary outcome will be estimates of bisphenol A exposures not associated with adverse effects on semen quality parameters, from both epidemiological studies and experimental studies with laboratory animals. For human epidemiological studies, the outcomes will be operationalised in terms of exposures associated with semen quality parameters not significantly different from referents. If most epidemiological studies are cross-sectional, the estimation of bisphenol A exposures not associated with adverse effects on semen parameters will rely on animal studies, due to difficulties with ruling out reverse causation in cross-sectional studies. For animal studies, the outcomes will be operationalised in terms of no-observed-adverse-effect-levels (NOAEL), lowest-observed-adverse-effect levels (LOAEL) or benchmark doses (lower limits). Studies that cover the period when germ cell populations are established during development (gestational day 7 to post-natal day 8 in the mouse; gestational day 9 to post-natal day 10 in the rat) will be prioritised.
Assessment of heterogeneity (6.3) and consequences of developing summary results (6.4)	
Effect modifiers for subgroup analysis	
Transformation of scales into common measures (6.2)	To enable quantitative comparisons between bisphenol A exposures in human studies and experimental studies with animals, we will convert urinary bisphenol A levels into daily intakes for humans by employing the toxicokinetic model detailed in Koch et al. (2012).
Assessment of publication bias (6.5)	
Impact of the risk of bias assessment on the synthesis (6.6)	The evidence synthesis will only consider human epidemiological studies rated as high or medium confidence, and experimental animal studies rated as high confidence (Tier 1).
Sensitivity analyses (6.7)	
Other methods	

Methods for synthesising the included evidence

Refer to section 6 of COSTER for detailed recommendations for how evidence should be synthesised in systematic reviews. Popay et al. (2006) attached provides very useful guidance on how to approach the non-quantitative components of the synthesis.

 [Popay et al. 2006 - Guidance on the Conduct of Narrative Synthesis in Systematic Reviews.pdf](#)

Step 22 skipped on Mar 26, 2021 20:11:43

- 22 Define the methods for determining how, given strengths and limitations of the overall body of evidence, confidence in the results of the synthesis of the evidence for each outcome is to be captured and expressed.** (For reviews which include multiple streams of evidence, this may need to be defined for each stream.) *Recommendation 1.4.5*

The components of assessment of confidence or certainty in the evidence are described in section 7 of COSTER.

Mar 26, 2021 20:13:40

The methods are defined a priori but have not been piloted at the stage of protocol development.

Step 22.1 skipped on Mar 26, 2021 20:11:43

- 22.1 Pilot the process for the assessment of confidence in the results of the synthesis of the evidence.** How will the review team be trained in use of the tool, and what are the conditions under which the piloting process will be determined satisfactory? *Recommendation 1.4.7*

Step 23 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:47:15

- 23 For reviews which include multiple streams of evidence (e.g. animal and human studies), define the methods for integrating the individual streams into an overall result.** *Recommendation 1.4.6*

This should include a description of the relative relevance of populations (e.g. species, age, comorbidities etc.), exposures (e.g. timing, dose), and outcomes (direct or surrogate, acute or chronic model of disease, etc.), as appropriate, per which inferences about predicted effects in target populations can be made from observed effects in study populations.

Registering and publishing the protocol

Step 24 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:47:18

- 24 Create a permanent public record of intent to conduct the review** (e.g. by registering the protocol in an appropriate registry) prior to conducting the literature search. *Recommendation 1.5.1*

Step 25 failed on Mar 26, 2021 19:49:30

- 25 As appropriate for review planning and question formulation, secure peer-review and public feedback on a draft**

version of the protocol, incorporating comments into the final version of the protocol. *Recommendation 1.5.2*

Step 26 completed on Mar 26, 2021 19:47:46

26 Publish the final version of the protocol in a public archive, prior to screening studies for inclusion in the review.
Recommendation 1.5.3

Publication of the protocol in a journal is equivalent to publication in a public archive.